

Standard Operating Procedure	Version: 2
Storage of ESBL <i>E. coli</i> / ESBL <i>K. pneumoniae</i> isolates, and BPW for future analysis.	
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Authors	Signed	Date
Madalitso Mphasa		01/08/19
Fiona Oruru		01/08/19
Dr Derek Cocker		01/08/19

Reviewer	Signed	Date
Dr Derek Cocker		01/08/19
Authoriser	Signed	Date
Dr Nicholas Feasey		01/08/19

Version History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	01/04/19	Initial version
2.0	01/08/19	Changes after initial pilot phase

1. Introduction

This method is applicable for the storage of cultured ESBL *E. coli* (ESBL -E) and ESBL *K. pneumoniae* (ESBL-K) isolates from stool (human / animal) and environmental samples and extracted DNA obtained from households included in the DRUM study.

The proportion of patients admitted to hospitals in Uganda and Malawi with invasive infections caused by ESBL resistant Enterobacteriaceae including ESBL-E and ESBL-K is increasing. Given the reduced availability of carbapenems, many of these drug-resistant infections are locally untreatable. To understand the drivers of this antimicrobial resistance, further evidence of the role of household environment contamination on human and animal carriage with ESBL-E and ESBL-K is required.

2. Purpose

This SOP concerns the storage plan of samples, cultured isolates of ESBL *E. coli* / *K. pneumoniae* and extracted DNA.

3. Responsibilities

- Field workers
 - Collection of human and animal stool, and environmental samples in according to Sample Collection SOPs
 - Correct labelling of collection samples
 - Prompt transport of collected samples to the laboratory
 - Completion of sample collection log
- Study Laboratory Technicians
 - Receive samples from field and complete sample collection log
 - Register samples on the DRUM teleform / eLIMS system
 - Double-check correct sample labelling
 - Processing ESBL positive samples in accordance with processing SOPs
 - Storage of samples for further analysis in accordance with this SOP
- Principal Investigators
 - Ensure laboratory training in sample processing procedures provided
 - Undertake quality control checks of laboratory processing.

4. Procedure

4.1. Stool Storage (Human and Animal)

4.2. Environmental Sample Storage (Swabs and Sponge-Sticks)

4.3. Environmental Sample Storage (Food)

4.4. Environmental Sample Storage (Water)

4.5 Test Procedure – Microbank Inoculation

1. Label a separate microbank vial corresponding to the correct number in the database for each organism to be stored (*E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*).
2. Using aseptic technique, unscrew the microbank vial.
3. Using a sterile inoculating loop pick off a single colony from the ESBL ChromAgar plates and place into the microbank vial.
4. Using aseptic technique, replace the cap on the microbank vial tightly, and invert it 4-5 times to emulsify the organism. Do not vortex.
5. Let the microbank vial sit for 2 minutes to allow the isolate to bind to the beads. Remove the cap and use a sterile disposable Pasteur pipette to remove the cryo-preserved. The beads should now be as free of liquid as possible.
6. Close the microbank vial (finger tight only). It is important that they are not overtightened.
7. Place the microbank vial in a Microbank storage box and freeze at -80°C.

4.6 Test Procedure – Plate Sweep

1. Take a 10µl loop and streak across the plate left to right and up / down, across the *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* isolates picking up multiple colonies.
2. If there is more than one colony colour of morphology, make sure that you pick up one of each type.
3. Then place this loop into a cryovial with BPW and glycerol, and store in the -80°C.

5. Recording storage location

The storage location is recorded on the study sample storage database. Log on to the laboratory computer. Select the visit and sample type (e.g. baseline visit stool sample); if a new box is needed, number them sequentially (1,2,3). Complete the sample ID by scanning the barcode and store the sample in the indicated location.

6. Health and Safety

Please refer to risk assessment tools and local health and safety guidelines